

Green synthesis of novel isoxazoline derivatives using *N*-phenyl- α -amino nitrone under microwave irradiation

Bhaskar Chakraborty* and Neelam Rai

Organic Chemistry Laboratory, Sikkim Government College, Gangtok-737 102, Sikkim, India

E-mail : bchakraborty42@gmail.com

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Abstract : Microwave assisted 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reaction of *N*-phenyl- α -amino nitrone with various alkynes as dipolarophile afforded novel isoxazoline derivatives with high synthetic potentials.

Keywords : MWI, cycloaddition reaction, novel isoxazolines.

Introduction

The utility of nitrones in synthetic organic chemistry has been widely illustrated¹. The main reactions involving nitrones are nucleophilic addition and 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition to olefins and acetylenes. 1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition reactions are among the most important synthetic routes for the construction of five-membered ring carbocycles and heterocyclic systems¹. Owing to the labile nature of the N–O bond under mild reducing conditions, isoxazolidines provide easy access to a variety of fascinating 1,3-difunctional aminoalcohols². The use of microwaves in organic synthesis has increased dramatically within the past decade, receiving widespread acceptance and becoming an indispensable tool^{3–5}. In continuation of our green methodological synthesis of spiro isoxazolidine, isoxazolidine, aldehyde, ketone synthesis using α -amino and α -chloro nitrones in solid phase and in hydrated media^{6–15}, we report herein microwave assisted green synthesis of some novel isoxazoline derivatives having high synthetic potential using *N*-phenyl- α -amino nitrone (**1**) with different alkynes with excellent yield (Scheme 1; Table 1).

Furthermore, synthetic potential of the novel isoxazoline derivatives (**2–4**) are tremendous as they could be converted into 1,3-difunctional amino alcohols (Scheme 2) by the reductive cleavage of the N–O bond of the isoxazolines (**2–4**) by simply heating the substrates with zinc powder in glacial acetic acid¹⁶. Detail studies are in progress with initial ¹H NMR data¹⁷.

R = C₆H₅; R₁ = NH₂

R₂ = C₆H₅; R₃ = COOCH₃

R₂ = COOCH₃; R₃ = COOCH₃

R₂ = R₃ = COOH

(i) Reaction condition : MWI, nitronium **1** (1 mmol), dipolarophile (1 equivalent), dry DMF, 4–5 min

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

For the present study, we have chosen alkynes like dimethyl acetylene dicarboxylate, phenyl methyl propiolate and acetylene dicarboxylic acid (but-2-ynedioic acid) respectively as dipolarophiles in 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reaction with *N*-phenyl- α -amino nitrone (**1**)^{6,13–15} for the synthesis of novel isoxazoline derivatives (**2–4**). These results can be rationalized by an exo approach of the nitronium (**1**) for the dipolarophiles (alkynes) in the development of novel cycloadducts (**2–4**) which have *Z*-configuration (transition state **1**)^{18,19}.

Stereochemistry of the novel isoxazoline derivatives (**2–4**) could not be determined in detail since two most important protons are absent at C₄ and C₅ positions and the lone singlet signal due to C₃ proton unable to predict

Table 1. Physicochemical data of synthesized novel isoxazoline derivatives (2-4)

Entry	Nitrone	Dipolarophile ^a	Time (min)	Cycloadduct ^b	Yield ^c (%)
1	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- α -amino nitrone (1)	Phenyl methyl propiolate	4	2 : Red viscous liquid	93
2	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- α -amino nitrone (1)	Dimethyl acetylene-dicarboxylate	5	3 : Dark yellow liquid	91
3	<i>N</i> -Phenyl- α -amino nitrone (1)	Acetylene dicarboxylic acid	5	4 : Colourless gummy liquid	90

^aReaction condition : Nitrone 1 (1 mmol), dipolarophile (1 equivalent), dry DMF, MWI.

^bAll the compounds were characterized by IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR, MS, HRMS spectral data.

^cIsolated yields after purification.

TS 1

it. Expected broad signal for amino groups at δ 3.05–2.80 ppm and sharp singlet for ester methyl protons at δ 1.50–1.20 ppm are obtained while carboxylic protons showed sharp singlet signals around δ 10.15 ppm in the ¹H NMR spectrum. The major and minor conformers of the novel isoxazoline ring systems (2-4) may be represented as Fig. 1.

$R_1 = \text{Me}; R_1 = \text{Ph}, R_2 = \text{COOCH}_3; R_1 = R_2 = \text{COOCH}_3;$
 $R_1 = R_2 = \text{COOH}; R_3 = -\text{NH}_2$

Fig. 1

All the cycloadducts are stable and prominent molecular ion peak, base peaks are obtained in the mass spectrum as expected.

In summary, we have demonstrated a convenient, inexpensive and highly efficient protocol for the synthesis of isoxazoline derivatives using *N*-phenyl- α -amino nitrone in 1,3-dipolar cycloaddition reaction under microwave irradiation. The notable factors of this methodology are : (a) excellent purity and high yields, (b) short reaction times and (c) operational simplicity and non-toxicity of the reactant reagents used. Therefore, it is believed that procedure described here will find important applications in the environment friendly synthesis of isoxazoline derivatives and thereby offering greater scope in cycloaddition reactions.

Experimental

PMR spectra were recorded with a Bruker DRX 300 spectrometer (300 MHz, FT NMR) using TMS as internal standard. CMR spectra were recorded on the same instrument at 75 MHz. The coupling constants (*J*) are given in Hz. IR spectra were obtained with a Perkin-Elmer RX 1-881 machine as film or as KBr pellets for all the products. MS spectra were recorded with a Jeol SX-102 (FAB) instrument. The HRMS spectra were recorded on a DART-HRMS, JMS-T100LC, Accu-TOF instrument. TLC's were run on Fluka silica gel precoated TLC plates while column chromatography was performed with silica gel (E. Merck, India) 60–200 mesh. All other reagents and solvents were purified after receiving from commercial suppliers. *N*-Phenylhydroxylamine was prepared following standard methods available in the literature and

has been used already for the synthesis of aldehydes/ ketones and cycloaddition reactions involving α -amino, α -chloro nitrones in aqueous phase and in solvent free conditions. Microwave irradiations were carried out using microwave oven KENSTER 19LKH, 19SSLM-2450 MHz.

General procedure of cycloaddition for isoxazoline derivatives (MWI) :

A mixture of nitrone **1** (1 mmol) and phenyl methyl propiolate (1 equivalent) in dry DMF (5 drops) was taken in a 25 ml Erlenmeyer flask and subjected to microwave irradiation at medium power (50%) for 4 min (entry 1). The completion of reaction was monitored by TLC ($R_f = 0.48$). The reaction mixture was cooled to RT and extracted with diethyl ether. The product was concentrated in a rotary evaporator and finally purified by recrystallization from ethanol to afford pure cycloadduct **2** (entry 1, Table 1, Scheme 1). This procedure was followed for other substrates listed in Table 1.

(S)-Methyl-3-amino-2,3-dihydro-2,5-diphenylisoxazole-4-carboxylate (2) :

IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} 3510–3415 (br), 3050 (s), 1754 (s), 1660 (m), 1360 (m), 772 (s) cm^{-1} ; PMR (CDCl_3) : δ_{H} 7.54–7.33 (2 \times 5H, m, C_6H_5 hydrogens), 3.35 (2H, br, $-\text{NH}_2$), 1.95 (1H, s, C_3H), 1.54 (3H, s, $-\text{COOCH}_3$); CMR (CDCl_3) : δ_{C} 172.66 (ester carbonyl carbons), 134.12, 132.76, 131.34, 130.75, 129.04, 128.25, 126.90, 126.22 (aromatic carbons), 84.16 (C_5), 73.44 (C_3), 52.92 (C_4), 23.35 ($-\text{COOCH}_3$), 17.82 ($-\text{COOCH}_3$); FAB-MS : m/z 296 (M^+), 219, 191, 175, 114, 105, 77; HRMS-EI : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$ (M), 296.1220, Found : M^+ , 296.1206.

(S)-Dimethyl-3-amino-2,3-dihydro-2-phenylisoxazole-4,5-dicarboxylate (3) :

IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} 3506–3426 (br), 3024 (s), 1750 (s), 1664 (m), 1340 (m), 770 (s) cm^{-1} ; PMR (CDCl_3) : δ_{H} 7.59–7.26 (5H, m, C_6H_5 hydrogens), 3.83 (2H, br, $-\text{NH}_2$), 1.70 (1H, s, C_3H), 1.25 (2 \times 3H, s, $-\text{COOCH}_3$); CMR (CDCl_3) : δ_{C} 170.23, 169.52 (ester carbonyl carbons), 130.10, 129.73, 129.14, 128.76 (aromatic carbons), 83.90 (C_5), 77.12 (C_3), 57.81 (C_4), 24.55, 23.74 ($-\text{COOCH}_3$), 19.43, 19.17 ($-\text{COOCH}_3$); FAB-MS : m/z 278 (M^+), 247, 219, 191, 175, 160, 87, 77, 59, 31; HRMS-EI : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$ (M), 278.1040, Found : M^+ , 278.1018.

(S)-3-Amino-2,3-dihydro-2-phenylisoxazole-4,5-dicarboxylic acid (4) :

IR (KBr) : ν_{\max} 3516–3428 (br), 3035 (s), 1725 (s), 1665 (m), 1345 (m), 766 (s) cm^{-1} ; PMR (CDCl_3) : δ_{H} 10.24 (2 \times 1H, s, COOH), 6.88–6.73 (5H, m, C_6H_5 hydrogens), 3.70 (2H, br, $-\text{NH}_2$), 1.82 (1H, s, C_3H); CMR (CDCl_3) : δ_{C} 173.69, 172.04 (carboxyl carbons), 135.06, 134.87, 132.86, 130.85 (aromatic carbons), 86.53 (C_5), 79.28 (C_3), 55.40 (C_4); FAB-MS : m/z 250 (M^+), 205, 177, 161, 100, 77, 73, 45; HRMS-EI : Calcd. for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$ (M), 250.0780, Found : M^+ , 250.0766.

Conclusion :

This contribution represents an extension of our studies dealing with the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds having isoxazoline cores in their structure. Further studies will be carried out in the near future to test their potential biological activities.

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